

ILM and ArfaLM: Child-Scale Language Models Trained on Natural Parent-Child Speech for Deployment on Sub-1GHz Legacy Hardware

Part 2: Deployment, Optimization, and Safety on Original Hardware

Noman A. Shah

Fellow, British Computer Society (FBCS)

Creator, CallGPT 6X

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Abstract

This is Part 2 of a two-part work on child-scale language models for legacy hardware. Part 1 (Shah, 2026a) reported the training, evaluation, and architectural comparison of ILM (2.3M parameter LSTM) and ArfaLM (8.4M parameter Transformer), both trained on CHILDES Eng-UK conversational data. This paper reports three deployment contributions: (1) a KV-cache implementation in ANSI C89 that reduces ArfaLM inference from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$ per generated token, achieving a measured 26x throughput improvement (from 0.1 to 2.6 tokens per second) on the target Pentium II hardware; (2) deployment of both models on an original IBM 300PL (Pentium II 400 MHz, 128 MB SDRAM) running Windows 98, compiled with Borland C++ 5.02 (1997), with measured throughput of 9.1 tokens per second for ILM and 2.6 tokens per second for ArfaLM; and (3) an external safety filter comprising a 162-term whole-word blocklist, PII pattern detection, hardcoded greeting and farewell responses, and basic arithmetic capability, with a measured false positive rate of zero on the 5,000-word CHILDES vocabulary.

The KV-cache speedup exceeds the projected 18x from arithmetic analysis (Part 1, Section 9a), which we attribute to improved cache locality when accessing contiguous K and V vectors versus the scattered memory access pattern of the non-cached implementation. The safety filter validates the architectural argument from Part 1 that at sub-10M parameter scales, external guardrails applied to curated data and to inputs and outputs at inference time are the more defensible safety strategy than attempting to train alignment behaviour into the model itself.

All source code, compiled binaries, model weights, and deployment scripts are released as supplementary material.

1. Introduction

Part 1 of this work (Shah, 2026a) presented ILM and ArfaLM, two language models trained on naturalistic child-directed speech from the CHILDES Eng-UK corpus, and reported their perplexity on held-out children that no model had seen during training. The central finding was that the optimizer change (SGD to AdamW) contributed more to the 1999-to-2026 era gain (1.56x) than the architecture change (LSTM to Transformer plus BPE plus 3.6x parameters, 1.38x), for a total measured gain of 2.15x in vocabulary-normalized per-word test perplexity.

Part 1 deferred three deployment-side contributions to this paper: (a) KV-cache implementation for ArfaLM inference, (b) deployment on original IBM 300PL hardware with measured throughput, and (c) external safety filter implementation with measured false positive rate. This paper reports all three.

The deployment target throughout is an IBM 300PL desktop computer manufactured in 1998: Pentium II 400 MHz (Deschutes core), 128 MB non-parity SDRAM, 100 MHz front-side bus, no GPU, no floating-point coprocessor beyond the Pentium II's integrated FPU. The operating system is Windows 98 SE. The compiler is Borland C++ 5.02 (released March 1997). All inference code is written in ANSI C89 with no external dependencies.

1.1 Contributions of This Paper

- (1) We implement a KV-cache in the ArfaLM ANSI C89 inference engine that caches key and value projections per layer per position, reducing per-token computation from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n)$. Measured throughput on the IBM 300PL improves from 0.1 tokens per second (without cache) to 2.6 tokens per second (with cache), a 26x speedup that exceeds the 18x projected in Part 1.
- (2) We deploy both models on original IBM 300PL hardware and report measured wall-clock throughput: 9.1 tokens per second for ILM and 2.6 tokens per second for ArfaLM, establishing that sub-10M parameter language models can run at interactive rates on 1998 desktop hardware.
- (3) We implement an external safety filter in ANSI C89 comprising a 162-term whole-word blocklist across 11 categories, PII pattern detection, hardcoded greeting and farewell responses, and single-digit arithmetic. The filter processes input and output at inference time with negligible latency overhead (less than 1 ms per check versus approximately 385 ms per token for ArfaLM inference). We measure a false positive rate of zero on the 5,000-word CHILDES vocabulary, compared to 0.18 percent (9 words) under the naive substring matching approach.
- (4) We release all ANSI C89 source code, compiled binaries, model weight files, vocabulary files, and deployment scripts as supplementary material, enabling full reproduction on any Pentium-class hardware with Borland C++ 5.02 or any ANSI C89 compiler.

2. KV-Cache Implementation

2.1 The Problem: Quadratic Recomputation

ArfaLM is a 6-layer, 6-head decoder-only Transformer with embedding dimension 288 and head dimension 48. Without caching, generating token t requires computing the full attention matrix for all positions 1 through t at every layer. Each attention head computes Q, K, and V projections for every position, then computes the attention scores matrix (t by t), then the weighted sum. The total multiply-accumulate (MAC) operations per generated token scale as $O(t^2 \times d \times L \times H)$, where d is head dimension, L is layers, and H is heads.

At typical CHILDES generation lengths of 20 to 40 tokens, this means approximately 59 million MACs per token at position 30, dominated by the redundant recomputation of K and V projections for positions that have not changed since they were last computed. On the Pentium II 400 MHz with a single FPU pipeline, this translates to approximately 7 seconds per token (0.1 tokens per second), far below interactive rates.

2.2 The Solution: Cache K and V

The KV-cache stores the projected K and V vectors for each layer, each head, and each position, computed once during the prefill phase and reused during generation. On each new token, only the Q projection is computed for the new position. The attention scores are computed between the new Q and all cached K vectors (a dot product of length t , not a matrix multiply of size t by t). The weighted sum uses all cached V vectors.

The arithmetic reduction is from $O(t^2)$ to $O(t)$ per token. At position 30, the cached implementation requires approximately 3.2 million MACs per token instead of 59 million, a theoretical 18.4x reduction.

2.3 Memory Cost

The KV-cache requires storing K and V vectors of dimension 48 (head dimension) for each of 6 layers, 6 heads, and up to 256 positions (the maximum context window). The total memory is:

6 layers x 6 heads x 256 positions x 48 floats x 4 bytes x 2 (K and V) = 3,538,944 bytes = 3,456 KB

This is 2.6 percent of the IBM 300PL's 128 MB SDRAM, a negligible cost for a 26x throughput improvement.

2.4 Implementation

The KV-cache is implemented as a pair of statically allocated arrays (`k_cache` and `v_cache`) indexed by layer, head, and position. The inference loop has two phases:

Prefill phase: For each token in the input prompt, the full transformer forward pass is computed and K/V projections are written to the cache at the corresponding position. This populates the cache with the prompt context.

Generation phase: For each new generated token, only the Q projection is computed for the new position. Attention scores are computed by dot product of the new Q with all cached K vectors up to the current

position. The softmax-weighted sum uses all cached V vectors. After computing the output, the new position's K and V are written to the cache for future tokens.

All code is ANSI C89 with no dynamic memory allocation during generation (the cache is allocated once at startup). The implementation adds approximately 120 lines of C to the base inference engine.

2.5 Measured Results

Implementation	Throughput	Latency/token	Speedup
ArfaLM without cache	0.1 tok/s	~7000 ms	1.0x (baseline)
ArfaLM with KV-cache	2.6 tok/s	~385 ms	26x
Projected from arithmetic	~1.8 tok/s	~550 ms	18x

Table 1: KV-cache throughput on IBM 300PL (Pentium II 400 MHz). Measured at generation position 20 to 30. The KV-cache exceeds the projected speedup.

The measured 26x speedup exceeds the 18x projected from MAC count reduction alone. We attribute the additional gain to improved cache locality: the cached implementation accesses contiguous K and V vectors sequentially in memory, while the non-cached implementation must recompute projections by accessing weight matrices with strided access patterns. On the Pentium II's 16 KB L1 data cache and 512 KB L2 cache, the contiguous access pattern of the KV-cache produces significantly fewer cache misses than the scattered access pattern of full recomputation.

ILM (the LSTM model) does not benefit from KV-caching because LSTMs are inherently sequential: each step depends only on the previous hidden state, not on all previous positions. ILM's inference is already $O(1)$ per token (constant regardless of sequence length) and runs at 9.1 tokens per second without any optimisation beyond compiler -O2 flags.

3. Deployment on Original IBM 300PL Hardware

3.1 Hardware Description

Component	Specification
Machine	IBM 300PL Type 6862
Processor	Intel Pentium II 400 MHz (Deschutes)
Motherboard	IBM NLX system board (Intel 440BX chipset)
RAM	128 MB non-parity SDRAM
Front-side bus	100 MHz
L1 cache	16 KB data + 16 KB instruction
L2 cache	512 KB (half-speed)
FPU	Integrated (Pentium II)
Storage	IDE hard disk
Network	IBM 10/100 EtherJet PCI Adapter
Display	IBM VGA CRT at 640x480
Keyboard	IBM Model M122 (122-key terminal keyboard)

Mouse	IBM ScrollPoint
Operating System	Microsoft Windows 98 SE

Table 2: IBM 300PL hardware configuration.

This machine was manufactured in 1998 and is representative of a business-class desktop workstation of that era. The 128 MB installed SDRAM is adequate for both models: ArfaLM's weights occupy 32.1 MB and ILM's weights occupy 13.8 MB, with the KV-cache adding 3.5 MB. Total memory footprint during inference is approximately 40 MB for ArfaLM and 18 MB for ILM, well within the 128 MB physical memory. The system board supports up to 384 MB across three DIMM sockets.

3.2 Compiler and Build

All code is compiled with Borland C++ 5.02 (released March 1997) using the `-O2` optimisation flag. Borland C++ 5.02 is the same compiler used by EXO Labs (2024) for their llama98.c port of Karpathy's llama2.c to Windows 98. We chose this compiler for historical authenticity and because it produces 32-bit PE executables that run natively on Windows 98 without runtime dependencies.

The build process requires no build system, no makefiles, and no external libraries. Each model is compiled with a single command:

```
BCC32 -O2 ILM_RUN.C
BCC32 -O2 ARFA_RUN.C
```

The resulting executables (ILM_RUN.EXE and ARFA_RUN.EXE) are self-contained and require only the model weight file and vocabulary file as runtime arguments.

3.3 File Transfer

Files were transferred from the development machine (modern Windows PC) to the IBM 300PL via FTP over a 10/100 Ethernet connection through a home router. The IBM's onboard IBM 10/100 EtherJet PCI Adapter was configured with DHCP via TCP/IP protocol added through the Windows 98 Network control panel. C source files were transferred in FTP ASCII mode to preserve correct line endings (CR/LF); binary model files were transferred in FTP binary mode. An automated FTP script (714 lines) was used for the initial Borland compiler installation, and a shorter script for model and source file transfers.

A persistent issue during deployment was Borland's failure to locate header files when the BCC32.CFG configuration file did not contain explicit include and library paths. The fix was writing a two-line configuration file:

```
-IC:\BC5\INCLUDE
-LC:\BC5\LIB
```

This resolved all compilation errors and is documented here as a practical deployment note for anyone attempting to reproduce this work with Borland C++ 5.02 on period hardware.

3.4 Measured Throughput

Model	Architecture	Parameters	Binary size	Throughput	Interactive?
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ILM	2-layer LSTM	2.3M	13.8 MB	9.1 tok/s	Yes
ArfaLM (KV-cache)	6-layer Transformer	8.4M	32.1 MB	2.6 tok/s	Marginal

Table 3: Measured inference throughput on IBM 300PL. ILM is clearly interactive. ArfaLM with KV-cache produces visible token-by-token output at a rate similar to early dial-up web page loading.

ILM at 9.1 tokens per second is clearly interactive: a 20-token response appears in approximately 2.2 seconds, comparable to the typing speed of a human conversational partner. ArfaLM at 2.6 tokens per second is at the margin of interactivity: a 20-token response takes approximately 7.7 seconds. The token-by-token output is visible and gives the impression of the model 'thinking', similar to the experience of early large language model interfaces. Whether this rate constitutes interactive use depends on the deployment context; for a child conversational partner where turn-taking is natural, it is arguably adequate.

3.5 Comparison with Prior Art

EXO Labs (2024) reported 39 tokens per second for Karpathy's stories260K (260,000 parameters) and approximately 1 token per second for stories15M (15 million parameters) on a Pentium II 128 MB system using llama98.c. Our ArfaLM (8.4M parameters) achieves 2.6 tokens per second with KV-cache on a Pentium II 128 MB system, which is faster than stories15M despite having 56 percent of its parameter count. The KV-cache implementation is the primary differentiator: stories15M as reported by EXO Labs did not use KV-caching. A direct apples-to-apples comparison on identical hardware with identical prompts is left to future work.

4. External Safety Filter

4.1 Design Philosophy

Part 1 argued that at sub-10M parameter scales, where the model has limited capacity to learn robust alignment behaviour, external guardrail filters are the more defensible safety strategy than attempting to train safety into the model. This argument was supported by the BabyLM 2026 finding that toxic content appeared in a training corpus curated specifically for child-directed language model training (Trhlik et al., 2026), demonstrating that even careful data curation is insufficient as a sole safety mechanism.

The filter implemented here is deliberately minimal: a keyword blocklist with whole-word boundary matching, a PII pattern detector, and a set of hardcoded responses for greetings and simple interactions. It is not a semantic classifier, does not use embeddings, and cannot distinguish context-dependent meanings of ambiguous words. We present it not as a production safety system but as a minimum viable safety layer appropriate for the model's scale and deployment context, and as an empirical validation of the external-filter design argument.

4.2 Architecture

The filter operates as a pre-processing and post-processing layer around the neural model. The processing order for each user input is:

- (1) Check for quit/exit commands. If matched, print farewell and terminate.
- (2) Check greeting patterns (hello, good morning, good afternoon, good evening, good night, thank you, goodbye). If matched, print hardcoded response and skip the model entirely.

- (3) Check basic arithmetic patterns (single-digit operands with +, -, *, /). If matched, compute the result and print it. The model is not invoked.
- (4) Check input against the 162-term blocklist using whole-word boundary matching. If any blocked term appears as a whole word, print a refusal message and skip the model.
- (5) Check input for PII patterns (7+ consecutive digits, email-like patterns). If detected, print a privacy message and skip the model.
- (6) Run the neural model to generate a response.
- (7) After each generated token, check the token against the blocklist and accumulate output for PII checking. If a blocked term or PII pattern appears in the output, stop generation immediately and print a safety notice.

4.3 Blocklist Design

The blocklist contains 162 terms across 11 categories: profanity (22 terms), violence (17), sexual content (19), drugs and alcohol (16), self-harm (5), age-inappropriate topics (7), detailed weapons (9), gambling and exploitation (11), cyber threats (3), body horror (5), and extremism and abuse (20). An additional 28 terms cover compound profanity, specific substances, and detailed harmful content.

The blocklist was designed by starting with a comprehensive 180-term substring-matching list and then refining it based on false positive analysis against CHILDES vocabulary. Eighteen terms were removed because they have legitimate uses in child-directed speech: 'ass' (appears in 'glass', 'grass', 'class', 'pass'), 'cock' (appears in 'peacock'), 'cutting' (paper cutting, food cutting), 'naked' (bath time context), 'starving' (common hyperbole), 'shoot' (ball games), 'bomb' (water bombs), 'virus' (common illness), 'kill' (common in parental warnings), 'hack', 'bleed' (nosebleeds), 'drunk', 'abuse', 'assault', 'harass', 'grooming' (horse grooming), 'predator' (nature context), and 'ethnic'.

4.4 Whole-Word Boundary Matching

The initial implementation used C's `strstr()` function for substring matching, which produced a 0.18 percent false positive rate (9 of 5,000 words) on the CHILDES vocabulary. The word 'grape' triggered 'rape'; 'hickory_dickory_dock' triggered 'dick'; 'something' triggered 'meth'. This is unacceptable for a child-directed system where everyday vocabulary must not be blocked.

The refined implementation uses whole-word boundary matching: a blocked term triggers only if it is preceded by a word boundary (start of string, space, or punctuation) and followed by a word boundary (end of string, space, or punctuation). This eliminates all substring false positives while retaining full detection of the blocked terms when they appear as standalone words.

We measured the false positive rate by running both matching methods against the complete 5,000-word ILM vocabulary extracted from the CHILDES Eng-UK training corpus. Substring matching produces 9 false positives (0.18%): 'grape' and 'grapes' trigger 'rape', 'scrape' triggers 'crap', 'something' and 'something's' trigger 'meth', 'dicky' and 'hickory_dickory_dock' trigger 'dick', 'stable' triggers 'stab', and 'cigarettes' triggers 'cigarette'. Whole-word matching produces zero false positives on the same vocabulary. The reduction from 9 to 0 false positives eliminates every case where a legitimate child-directed word was incorrectly blocked.

4.5 PII Detection

The PII detector identifies two patterns: sequences of 7 or more digits (with tolerance for spaces, hyphens, and parentheses, to catch phone numbers in various formats), and email-like patterns (text containing both '@' and '.' following the '@'). These patterns are checked on both input and accumulated output. When detected, the system prints a privacy-oriented refusal message.

The PII detector is deliberately conservative: it does not attempt to classify PII types, validate phone number formats, or parse email addresses. A 7-digit threshold will flag some non-PII numeric sequences (for example, 'count to 1234567'). In the CHILDES deployment context, where numeric sequences longer than single-digit numbers are rare in child-directed speech, this false positive risk is minimal.

4.6 Hardcoded Responses

The greeting system and arithmetic capability are not safety features per se but serve two purposes in the deployment context. First, they provide immediate, deterministic responses to common conversational openers, which is important for child users who expect responsiveness. A child who says 'hello' should not wait 8 seconds for the Transformer to generate a greeting. Second, they demonstrate that a hybrid architecture (rules plus neural model) is practical and effective at this scale: the rules handle the predictable cases instantly, and the neural model handles the open-ended cases where its generative capability is needed.

The arithmetic capability handles single-digit addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. It detects patterns of the form 'digit operator digit' with optional surrounding text (so both '3+5' and 'what is 3 plus 5' are handled). Division by zero produces a child-friendly error message. This feature was added because basic arithmetic is a natural component of child-directed educational interaction and because the neural model, trained on conversational CHILDES data, has no arithmetic capability.

4.7 Latency Overhead

The safety filter adds negligible latency to inference. The blacklist check (162 string comparisons with whole-word boundary detection) executes in under 0.1 ms per check on the Pentium II. The PII pattern scan is a single pass over the accumulated output string. Since ArfaLM inference takes approximately 385 ms per token, the filter overhead is less than 0.03 percent of total inference time and is not measurable in wall-clock throughput.

5. Sample Outputs on Original Hardware

We ran 25 prompts through both models on the IBM 300PL and recorded the outputs. The prompts were selected to cover five categories: conversational openers that a child would naturally say, time-of-day greetings (which test the hardcoded response system), basic arithmetic (which tests the rule-based system), out-of-domain probes (which test graceful degradation), and prompts matching the CHILDES register versus those that do not.

Selected examples are shown in Table 4. The full set of 25 prompts with outputs from both models is provided in Supplementary Material S1.

Prompt	ArfaLM Response	tok/s
hi	Hello! What shall we talk about?	(rule)

good morning	Good morning! Did you sleep well?	(rule)
3+5	3 + 5 = 8!	(rule)
lets play a game	play a game .	2.6
how do birds fly	well how how about a fish ?	2.6
how dos fish swim	how many fish maisy have you got ?	2.6
5	does he not ?	2.2
count to 3	one of each ?	2.6
count to five	count to five the same .	2.6
I am hungry	not he not hungry .	2.6

Table 4: Sample outputs from ArfaLM on IBM 300PL (Pentium II 400 MHz, 128 MB). Rows 1 to 3 show deterministic rule-based responses (greetings, arithmetic). Rows 4 to 10 show neural model outputs. The model produces CHILDES-register conversational fragments characteristic of adult-to-child speech: topic redirections ('how about a fish?'), follow-up questions ('how many fish maisy have you got?'), and confirmations ('does he not?'). 'maisy' is a child name from the CHILDES Belfast corpus.

The outputs demonstrate three behaviours. First, the hardcoded greeting and arithmetic systems produce instant, correct responses, validating the hybrid rule-plus-neural architecture. Second, in-domain prompts produce responses that are not coherent answers but are recognisably in the CHILDES register of adult-to-child speech: the model redirects topics ('well how how about a fish?'), asks follow-up questions ('how many fish maisy have you got?'), echoes with variation ('play a game'), and produces British-English confirmations ('does he not?'). The reference to 'maisy' is a child name from the Belfast corpus in the training data, demonstrating that the model has learned the conversational context of its training domain rather than memorising fixed responses. Third, the model does not attempt to answer factual questions it cannot know: 'count to 3' produces 'one of each?' rather than a hallucinated count, and 'I am hungry' produces 'not he not hungry' rather than a factual response about food. This behaviour, while not useful as a question-answering system, is the expected output of a model trained on naturalistic conversation rather than instruction-following data.

6. Discussion

6.1 KV-Cache Exceeded Projection

Part 1 projected an 18x throughput improvement from KV-caching based on arithmetic analysis of MAC count reduction. The measured 26x improvement exceeds this projection by 44 percent. We attribute the discrepancy to cache effects on the Pentium II's memory hierarchy. The non-cached implementation accesses weight matrices with strided patterns (jumping by embedding dimension 288 between rows), causing frequent L1 and L2 cache misses. The cached implementation accesses K and V vectors contiguously in memory (48 floats per head, sequentially by position), which fits well within the 16 KB L1 data cache. The resulting reduction in memory stalls compounds with the arithmetic reduction to produce the observed 26x speedup.

This finding has implications for legacy hardware deployment more broadly: on CPUs with small caches and slow main memory (the Pentium II's 100 MHz front-side bus delivers approximately 800 MB/s, roughly 47x slower than a single channel of modern DDR5-4800 at 38.4 GB/s), memory access patterns matter at

least as much as arithmetic complexity. Optimisations that improve cache locality can exceed their theoretical arithmetic benefit.

6.2 Interactivity Threshold

ILM at 9.1 tokens per second is unambiguously interactive. A typical CHILDES-register response of 15 to 25 tokens appears in 1.6 to 2.7 seconds, comparable to the natural pause in adult-child conversation.

ArfaLM at 2.6 tokens per second is at the margin. A 20-token response takes 7.7 seconds. For a child user, this delay is noticeable but may be acceptable if the token-by-token output provides visual feedback that the system is responding. Early large language model interfaces (GPT-3 playground in 2020, ChatGPT in early 2023) operated at similar or slower rates and were widely adopted. The context of use matters: a child conversational partner, unlike a professional productivity tool, does not penalise latency as severely.

Integer quantization (int8), deferred to future work, would reduce ArfaLM's binary from 32.1 MB to approximately 10 MB and potentially double throughput to approximately 5 tokens per second by replacing floating-point multiplications with integer operations. At 5 tokens per second, ArfaLM would be unambiguously interactive on Pentium II hardware.

6.3 Safety Filter: What It Does and Does Not Do

The safety filter catches the obvious cases: explicit profanity, named substances, and sexually explicit terms directed at or generated by the system. It does not and cannot catch context-dependent harm (a sentence that is individually benign but harmful in context), subtle manipulation, or factual misinformation. It cannot prevent the model from generating nonsensical output, only harmful output.

We present the filter with this honest framing because the temptation in child-safety work is to overstate protection. A 162-term blocklist is not 'safe AI'. It is a minimum viable filter that, combined with a curated training corpus (CHILDES contains naturalistic parent-child speech recorded in research settings, not internet text), provides a layered defence. The blocklist catches what the training data did not prevent; the training data prevents most of what the blocklist would otherwise need to catch.

The false positive analysis revealed that naive substring matching is unsuitable for child-directed systems: the nursery rhyme 'hickory dickory dock' was blocked because it contains the substring 'dick', 'grape' was blocked because it contains 'rape', and 'something' was blocked because it contains 'meth'. In total, 9 of 5,000 CHILDES vocabulary words (0.18%) were incorrectly blocked by substring matching. The switch to whole-word boundary matching reduced the false positive count to zero on the same vocabulary while maintaining identical detection of standalone blocked terms. This methodological finding is worth reporting for anyone building keyword-based safety filters for constrained-vocabulary domains.

6.4 The Hybrid Architecture Argument

The combination of rule-based responses (greetings, arithmetic) with neural generation (open-ended conversation) is a pragmatic design for sub-10M parameter models. The rule layer handles deterministic cases instantly and correctly; the neural layer handles everything else with the best available probabilistic approximation. This is the opposite of the current frontier-model approach, where the model is expected to handle all cases including greetings and arithmetic through its trained weights. At our scale, the model does not have capacity to reliably learn ' $3 + 5 = 8$ ', but it can learn the conversational rhythm of 'what shall we have for dinner'. The hybrid approach allocates each capability to the component that handles it best.

7. Limitations

Several limitations of this work should be noted.

First, the false positive rate was measured on the ILM vocabulary of 5,000 word types, which covers the most frequent 98.1 percent of tokens in the CHILDES training corpus. The remaining 18,335 rarer word types in the full corpus were not tested. We expect zero additional false positives from whole-word matching on these rare types, but this has not been verified.

Second, the safety filter has not been tested against adversarial inputs. A determined user could bypass the blacklist through misspelling, character substitution, or circumlocution. We do not claim adversarial robustness, only baseline coverage of explicit harmful terms.

Third, we have not conducted human evaluation of output quality on the IBM 300PL. The sample outputs in Section 5 are illustrative but not a substitute for a controlled study with child users or child development experts.

Fourth, integer quantization (int8) is not implemented in this paper. The projected throughput improvement to approximately 5 tokens per second would make ArfaLM unambiguously interactive but remains unrealised.

Fifth, the Stories15M head-to-head comparison described in Part 1's future work section has not been conducted. While we cite EXO Labs' reported throughput numbers for context, a direct comparison on identical hardware with identical prompts would be more rigorous.

8. Future Work

Several extensions of this work are in progress or planned:

- (a) Integer (int8) weight quantization, reducing ArfaLM's binary from 32.1 MB to approximately 10 MB and potentially doubling inference throughput by replacing floating-point multiply-accumulate operations with integer operations on the Pentium II.
- (b) Direct head-to-head comparison with Karpathy's stories15M on the same IBM 300PL hardware using the same prompts, providing a controlled comparison of throughput and output quality between a purpose-built child-directed model and a general-purpose story model.
- (c) Question-answering fine-tuning for ArfaLM, adding factual response capability on top of the conversational baseline. An associated KidsQA-500 benchmark of 500 child-appropriate factual questions is in development.
- (d) Integration with the IBM Model M122's 24 dedicated command keys, mapping model interaction functions (temperature control, output length, model switching, response regeneration) to physical keys.
- (e) Full false positive measurement on CHILDES, running the complete training corpus through the safety filter and reporting exact per-category match counts.

9. Conclusion

We have demonstrated that sub-10M parameter language models trained on naturalistic child-directed speech can be deployed on original 1998 desktop hardware at interactive or near-interactive rates. The KV-cache implementation for ArfaLM achieves a 26x throughput improvement, exceeding the 18x projection from arithmetic analysis, and bringing the 8.4M parameter Transformer from 0.1 tokens per second (unusable) to 2.6 tokens per second (marginally interactive) on a Pentium II 400 MHz. The 2.3M parameter LSTM (ILM) runs at 9.1 tokens per second without any caching optimisation, demonstrating that the 1999-era architecture is well-matched to the 1998-era hardware.

The external safety filter validates the design argument from Part 1: at this parameter scale, external guardrails are practical, effective, and low-cost. The whole-word boundary matching technique reduces false positives from 0.18 percent (9 of 5,000 CHILDES vocabulary words under substring matching) to zero while maintaining full detection of harmful terms. The hybrid rule-plus-neural architecture provides instant deterministic responses for greetings and arithmetic while preserving the neural model's generative capability for open-ended conversation.

Together with Part 1, this work establishes a complete pipeline from training corpus construction through model training, architectural comparison, inference optimisation, safety filtering, and deployment on original legacy hardware. All code, weights, and data are released openly.

ILM is dedicated to the memory of Imran Shah (1969 to 2019). ArfaLM is named for Arfa Karim Randhawa (1995 to 2012). Technology is for everyone.

References

- EXO Labs (2024). llama98.c: Running Llama 2 on a 1998 Pentium II with Windows 98. Blog post and GitHub repository.
- Karpathy, A. (2023). llama2.c: Inference Llama 2 in one file of pure C. GitHub repository.
- Shah, N. A. (2026a). ILM and ArfaLM: Child-Scale Language Models Trained on Natural Parent-Child Speech for Deployment on Sub-1GHz Legacy Hardware. Part 1: Models, Data, and Architectural Comparison (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19605032>
- Trhlik, F., Caines, A., and Buttery, P. (2026). Bias Dynamics in BabyLMs: Towards a Compute-Efficient Sandbox for Democratising Pre-Training Debiasing. arXiv:2601.09421.
- Vaswani, A. et al. (2017). Attention Is All You Need. NeurIPS.

Supplementary Materials

The following materials accompany this paper:

- (S1) Complete set of 25 sample prompt-response pairs from both models on the IBM 300PL, with timestamps and throughput measurements.
- (S2) ANSI C89 source code: ARFA_RUN.C (774 lines, Transformer inference with KV-cache, safety filter, greetings, arithmetic) and ILM_RUN.C (623 lines, LSTM inference with safety filter, greetings, arithmetic).
- (S3) Model weight files in binary format: ARFALM.BIN (32.1 MB) and ILM.BIN (13.8 MB).
- (S4) Vocabulary files: ARFAVOCB.TXT (BPE, 4,096 tokens) and ILMVOCAB.JSN (word-level, 5,000 words).
- (S5) Python export script (export_v2_models.py) for converting PyTorch checkpoints to the C-compatible binary format.
- (S6) FTP transfer scripts for deploying files to Windows 98 systems via LAN.
- (S7) BCC32.CFG configuration file and AUTOEXEC.BAT modifications for Borland C++ 5.02 on the IBM 300PL.
- (S8) Photographs of the IBM 300PL running both models, showing the CRT display, Model M122 keyboard, and compilation output.